

THE COMFORT PROPERTY OF NONWOVEN FABRIC : A REVIEW

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Abstract:

Nonwoven is an engineered product made from fibrous material. The random porous structure of nonwoven is a key characteristic. Therefore, it is suitable for various applications like medical textiles and cold weather jackets etc. This paper discussed the understanding of the structure and manufacturing method of nonwoven. It also reviews the comfort properties like thermal conductivity, air permeability, and moisture vapor transmission for various nonwoven fabrics produced using synthetic, natural fibre, blends, and specialty fibers. The methods to enhance the thermal properties of nonwoven are discussed, the thermal properties are enhanced by incorporating aerogel in structure and vertical layering of the fiber in the nonwoven.

Keywords: *nonwoven, porous, thermal conductivity, air permeability, moisture vapor transmission, aerogel, electromagnetic shielding,*

Introduction:

Nonwovens are innovative [1], engineered and high-tech fabrics made from fibers. They are used in a wide range of consumer and industrial products in combination with other materials or alone.

Nonwovens are designed for their specific application, ranging from thin, lightweight nonwovens to strong and durable nonwovens, be it consumer or industrial applications. The combination of their specific characteristics through the selection of raw materials, the formation and bonding methods, or the applied finishing treatments, such as printing, embossing, laminating, allow high-performance products to be delivered.

"A nonwoven is an engineered fibrous assembly, primarily planar, which has been given a designed level of structural integrity by physical and/or chemical means, excluding weaving, knitting or paper making."

As in case of woven and knit fabrics [2], the structure of the fabric in conjunction with properties of the constituent fibres and yarns determine the properties of the fabrics, and so is the case in the case of nonwovens. The structure of nonwovens is described primarily in terms of fibre packing and directional arrangement. Sometimes, the geometry of pores in nonwoven

Fibre packing Arrangement:

It is expressed in terms of packing density[2] which is nothing but fibre volume fraction in the fabric volume. Let volume of the fabric is V_f and volume of the all fibers the fabric is V . We can write packing density as

$$\mu = \frac{V}{V_f}$$

This can also be expressed in terms of the density of material

$$\mu = \frac{\rho^*}{\rho}$$

Where, ρ^* is fabric density and ρ is fibre density

Pore structure in nonwovens

A nonwoven fabric[2] generally consists of large number of fibers and a large (volume) portion of this material is occupied by air. This plane consists of numerous fibers and many air spaces. The air space

in the structure is called pore. Figure 1 shown the pore in fabric. We will now study the structure of these pores present in such an elementary plane of a nonwoven fabric.

Figure 1: Pores in the structure

Method of manufacturing of nonwovens:

The nonwoven manufacturing goes under four different stages namely, fiber preparation, web formation, bonding and finishing. There are various ways to produce nonwoven like Needle punch, Spunlace, Thermal bonding, chemical bonding and spunbond/meltblown. The fabric produced from different technology has different fabric characteristics.

Clothing and comfort:

it is one of the most important aspects of clothing. Comfort has been defined by many researchers in different terms [3]

- Physiological reaction of the wearer influences the comfort
- Temperature regulation mechanism of is the comfort
- Absence of unpleasantness is termed as comfort
- Comfort is a state of pleasant psychological, physiological, and physical harmony between a human being and the environment.

Comfort and satisfaction with clothing are influenced by both characteristics of clothing as well as by attitudinal and psychological perceptions of the wearer. The clothing characteristics is influenced by fibre and fabric properties, tactile, design of clothing, brand, care instruction and price.

Human–clothing interactions:

Clothing protects [3] the wearer from the environmental hazards for which it was made, and at the same time, it hinders the free evaporation of sweat from the skin.

The human clothing system contains several interconnected mechanisms that are crucial for maintaining the proper body temperature. If any one of these links fails to transfer heat, the body temperature may rise, and the wearer may experience sickness or dizziness as a result.

Under normal condition where environmental temperature is lower than the body temperature, heat flow from the body should be hindered by the clothing. If temperature difference between body and environment is low, then thermal insulation is required to wearer from the clothing. Clothing will prevent heat loss by enhancing the thermal insulation.

Evaluations of comfort properties:

The ability of the fabric to maintain skin temperature by transferring heat and perspiration from a person's body is an important factor in making clothing comfortable. Thermal comfort, which is one

of the most essential characteristics in buying textile and garment products today, has been considered a significant feature by many consumers. Generally speaking, the transmission of air, heat and water vapour from a garment is likely to be essential to clothes' comfort. Thermal properties are among the most important features of textiles. However, in the textile industry, it is vital that certain individual factors, namely size, shape and aesthetic behaviour like softness, smoothness and drape are considered.

- Air permeability:

The amount of [4] air that can move through fabric of 100 mm² in second at 10 mm head of water a pressure difference in milliliters is known as air permeability.

- Thermal conductivity:

Amount of heat [5] conducted through unit area of slab in a unit of time with a unit temperature difference between its faces.

- Moisture vapour permeability:

The moisture vapour permeability [4] is the ability fabric to allow vapour to pass through the fabric of per square meter per 24 hours in grams

Studies on the comfort property of Nonwoven

A lot of researchers have studied the use of nonwoven structures as a promising way to develop certain functional clothing products. Essentially, they studied the comfort aspects of nonwoven structures comprehensively. This paper reviews work on nonwoven structures and their physical comfort aspects.

Abu Shaid et al [6] studied developed aero-gel nonwoven with commercially available areo-gel nonwoven the SEM image is given below.

Figure 2: SEM images of developed aerogel-nonwoven surface

In this study aerogel was embedded between two needle punch nonwoven fabric produced from viscose fiber of 1.5 den and 38 mm length and. The aerogel of particle size and surface area are of 7-11 μm and of 700-800 m^2/g respectively. The nonwoven fabric samples were tested for various physical properties like thickness, areal density, tensile and bursting strength, flexural rigidity and bending modulus various thermal resistant properties.

After testing the sample, it was found that the flexural rigidity and modulus is lower in case of developed aerogel nonwoven fabric.

The developed aerogel-nonwoven shows similar thermal protection including dry and radiative heat resistance when it is compared with commercial sample. Because of its high stiffness and thickness, as well as non-compressibility, commercial fabric demonstrated higher heat resistance performance.

The aerogel-nonwoven fabrics shows high air and moisture vapor permeability than commercial one which contribute better thermal comfort.

The ability of surgical garments to prevent cross-infection between patients and medical staff is crucial. In order to minimize physiological stress on the wearer, it must also meet the standards for thermal comfort.

In this study suitability of SMS fabric for surgical application was done [7]. The three sample of 35 GSM, 50 GSM and 80 GSM produced by SMS technology. The SMS was also compared with breathable and water impermeable membrane laminated with knitted structure. The thermal properties like thermal conductivity, resistance, air and water vapour permeability, water vapour resistance were assessed.

After analysing the data of test result, it shows that air and water vapour permeability values fell as fabric weight grew, nonwoven textile showed higher thermal conductivity, resistance, absorptivity, and water vapour resistance. The thermal conductivity, thermal resistance, thermal, diffusion, and water vapour resistance values of the layered nonwoven constructions with a breathable and water impermeable membrane were higher. As areal density of fabric increased and membrane added, thermal comfort performances of nonwoven disposable gowns had decreased.

Thermophysiological comfort for protective clothing of multilayer nonwoven with aerogel or PCMS was studied by *Agnieszka Greszta et al*, [8]. Raw material used for the experiment are Polyester of 0.7 dtex/38 mm and bicomponent fibers of 5.4 dtex/ 52 mm were used to manufacture needle-punched nonwovens. Particle size of aerogel and PCM is 100-700 μm and 15-30 μm respectively. Particle density of aerogel is 120-150 kg/m^3 and PCM has $\sim 555 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3$. The nonwoven inserts with aerogel/PCMs were made based on 4 layers of needle punched nonwovens and shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: Multilayer nonwoven with silica aerogel/PCM granule

The additives are added between two layers of nonwoven and further bonded by heating pressure causes low melt and this molten mass sticks to nearby and hence bonding will take place. The reference sample is produced by bonding of only needle punch nonwoven.

After testing, it was found that the developed aerogel inserts shows lower thermal conductivity this is because of porous structure of aerogel and PCM microcapsule do not has significant effect on thermal conductivity. Increase in aerogel content in nonwoven will not have significant effect on thermal conductivity. DSC analysis showed high efficiency in absorbing and releasing heat for PCM containing nonwoven, thus regulating microclimate temperature in undergarment. Nonwoven containing aerogel

and PCM material showed lower highest water vapour transmission as compared to the reference sample. This is because of higher thickness and lower porosity of nonwoven fabric containing additives. Due to additives significant reduction in air permeability was found, but PCM noted higher decrease, this may be due to non-porous structure of PCM.

Cheema S.M. et al. studied the thermophysiological comfort of hydroentangle nonwoven and woven fabrics for the apparel industry [9]. During his research, he developed nonwoven fabric, which is produced from Tencel and bicomponent fibre, has been evaluated and compared with commercially available woven and hydroentangled nonwoven fabrics. The developed nonwoven fabric is bonded by using needle punch and hydroentanglement. The fabric was tested and analyzed for various properties like moisture management and thermal comfort properties. Nonwoven fabric with Tencel and bicomponent shows higher thickness as compared to other fabrics. The higher thickness causes loss of structure and results in higher air permeability. The air permeability is going to affect the thermal characteristics of the fabric. Higher air permeability gives a slower rate of heat transfer to the environment; this is because of the large numbers of pores in the structure. A higher number of pores means more entrapped air which will restrict the heat transfer process. Developed fabric shows higher wicking properties as compared to other fabrics. Higher wicking is due to the open structure, and fibrillated structure will create fine capillaries in the structure.

Viju et al. [10] developed the needle punch nonwoven using nettle fibres. Mild alkaline treatment was employed on nettle fibre to improve fibre flexibility. The effect of process parameters, namely, needle punch density, depth of penetration and fabric areal density on thermal conductivity, air permeability and water absorbency, were studied using Box-Behnken design of experiments. The needle punch density (punches/cm²) was kept in the range of 50 to 100, depth of penetration (mm) in the range of 8 to 12 mm and areal density (g/m²) in the field of 150 to 350. A total of 15 samples were produced according to Box-Behnken design. The thickness and areal density of the nonwoven fabric Thermal conductivity, air permeability and areal density of the developed fabric were analysed using ASTM D7340-07, ASTM D 737-36 and ASTM D 6242-98 standard testing methods.

They observed that thermal conductivity of the nonwoven ranges from 0.0251 W/mK to 0.0345 W/mK. They noticed that the major contributing factors to thermal conductivity were the thickness and porosity of the fabric. The thermal conductivity was noticed to increase with the increase in porosity. Lower-thickness fabric showed maximum thermal conductivity and vice versa. The sorption capacity of fabric was noticed to be higher for higher porosity fabric. The air permeability of the fabric was noticed to change with the porosity of the fabric. The higher the porosity, the higher the air permeability. Further, they observed that the punch density 75 punches/cm², 8 mm depth of penetration and 150 g/m² areal density produced nonwoven with maximum water absorbency 494%, air permeability 79 79 cm³/cm²/s and 0.00251 W/mK thermal conductivity.

Hassan, M.Z et al. [11] prepared the hydroentangled nonwoven fabric using comber noil. Comber noil is the by-product of a yarn spinning mill. During- the hydroentanglement process, fibres are entangled through high-pressure water jets. They varied the water jet pressure (WJS) and web conveyor speed (CS) and studied their effect on hydro-entangled nonwoven fabric's mechanical and comfort attributes. The hydroentangled nonwovens were prepared using 100% bleached cotton, having a mean length of 20.4mm. The parallel laid webs were exposed to different water jet pressures (5.0, 6.5, 8.0, 9.5, 11.0 MPa), keeping a constant web speed of 25 m/min for fibre bonding. Additionally, four fabrics were produced at 8.0 MPa WJP at different CS of 30, 35, 40 and 45 m/min. The areal density of all nonwovens was maintained at 55 g/m². It has been noticed that the tensile strength of fabric increased with an increase in water jet pressure at fixed conveyor speed. The higher the water jet pressure, the higher the transferred energy, which produced more entanglement in the fabric structure. Increased tensile strength is attributed to increased frictional constraint owing to higher fibre entanglement. They also noticed that the fabric thickness reduces with increased specific energy. Subsequently, the air permeability of fabric

was also observed to be reduced at high water jet pressure and low conveyor speed. Further, they observed that the thermal resistance decreased at higher water jet pressure and lower conveyor speed. This was due to the creation of densified structure at WJS and lower CS. The densified structure entraps less still air which is responsible for thermal insulation. They also evaluated the impact of WJS and CS on moisture management properties on nonwoven fabrics. It was found that fabric exhibits poor moisture management properties at higher WJS and lower CS. They concluded that WJS and CS can produce fabric structures as per properties application requirements.

Miao Yu et al. studied the comfort properties of clothing containing ultrafine polyester waddings [12]. Two different waddings having areal density 70 g/m^2 and 80 g/m^2 were chosen for study. Also, hollow polyester wadding of two kinds (60 g/m^2 and 80 g/m^2) was chosen as a contrast. The clothing comfort properties of the materials were evaluated subjectively and objectively. FTD 17 Thermal manikin was kept for objective evaluation in the climatic chamber (at $16 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, RH $70 \pm 2\%$). Clothing was evaluated subjectively by employing six male subjects. After wearing four clothing ensembles, they performed a rest-exercise-rest cycle. They rested for ten minutes to adapt to the climate chamber's environment. Five minutes later, wearing experimental clothing, they assessed the thermal and moisture sensation. Later, Participants utilised the VE-310 circular ergometer at a pace of 60 rotations per minute for ten minutes. Subsequently, they provided a renewed assessment of their comfort perceptions. The final evaluation of sensation was conducted after a post-exercise resting period of fifteen minutes. Subsequently, they compared clothing wearing properties of all the materials. It was observed that the thickness ratio for ultrafine polyester and hollow polyester fabric for equivalent weight was $1/2$. However, the corresponding thermal insulation ratio seen was about $1/0.9$. This signifies that the fabric made from ultrafine would keep the body warmer despite lower bulk. Furthermore, they observed that the ultrafine polyester wadding gives better thermal comfort at equal weights. In the wearer trial, they found that the clothing having a lining of 35% ultrafine polyester blended with 65% polyvinyl was most comfortable because of clothing was not increased air humidity. Finally, they concluded that ultrafine polyester fabric shoes have good thermal properties compared to hollow polyester. Nevertheless, the air permeability and moisture vapour transmission were poor than hollow-core polyester wadding. Therefore, the most comfortable properties of ultrafine polyester nonwoven wadding still need to be improved.

Wiah Wardiningsiha et al. investigated vertically lapped nonwoven fabrics force attenuation capacity and thermophysiological wear comfort [13]. They chose three different materials, namely, 3D vertically lapped nonwoven, vertically lapped nonwoven covered with single jersey knitted fabric and commercially available polyurethane closed-cell foam as material for hip protective pads for this study. Then they evaluated these materials for their attenuation force using the drop tower test method. This method generates impact energy by falling mass, which drops vertically on the fabric assembly. The fabric assembly contains artificial flesh from soft translucent silicone and a nonwoven structure. Then the impact energy of all these fabrics was recorded using a load cell placed beneath the fabric assembly. They observed that the artificial flesh alone gives maximum impact force above the fracture threshold. The mean impact force of vertically lapped nonwoven was observed to be equivalent to that of closed-cell foam. This was attributed to the form and geometry of the material. They noticed that when four sheets of uncovered nonwovens stacked over one another and impacted with the dropper, the resultant thickness of assembly was lower compared to covered nonwovens, resulting in a higher force of attenuation capacity. Furthermore, they examined fabric assemblies' dry thermal and evaporative resistance. They noticed that the thermal resistance of fabric assembly increases as the number of layers increases. Similarly, the evaporative resistance increased with an increase in number of layers. Further, they found that the dry thermal resistance of vertically lapped nonwoven was identical to that of closed-cell foam. However, the layered nonwoven fabric assembly possess the lowest evaporative resistance

to closed-cell foam. Finally, they concluded that vertically lapped nonwoven fabric is suitable for soft hip-protective pads. It would protect bone because of similar force attenuation to closed-cell foam.

Dan Wang *et al.* [14] studied the electromagnetic shielding effectiveness of copper-plated nonwoven fabric and its' related comfort properties. The properties like air permeability, water vapour permeability and thermal resistance were evaluated for various copper-plated nonwoven fabrics. It has been demonstrated that, as a result of this copper plating method, electromagnetic shielding efficiency is positively correlated with the amount of plated copper. The results of other tests demonstrate that this material's air permeability and water vapour permeability are negatively correlated to the effectiveness of its electromagnetic shielding. On the other hand, their heat resistance is positively associated with electromagnetic shielding performance. Besides these, the correlation of air permeability and water vapour permeability with optical porosity is favourable as well as thermal resistance is positive about volume porosity.

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